

Tandem Organic Light-Emitting Devices using C60 and Pentacene as a pure Organic Connecting Layer

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Abstract: A pure organic system of fullerene(C60)/pentacene has been investigated as a connecting unit for tandem organic light emitting devices with two identical emissive units consisting of NPB /Alq₃ exhibited better current efficiency and current density characteristics over conventional devices. The connecting unit shows superior optical transparency, resulting in minimal microcavity effect in the devices.

1. INTRODUCTION

Tandem organic light-emitting devices(OLEDs) have received considerable attention recently because of their high current efficiency and long lifetime[1-2]. Tandem OLEDs generally consists of two or more emissive units connected electrically in series via connecting unit. Under an applied electric field, electrons and holes are generated within the connecting unit and are injected into adjoining elements. Electroluminescence intensity of the tandem device thus is principle can linerly increase with the number of emissive units. It is obvious that performance of tandem OLEDs depends critically on how efficient efforts have been put on the exploration of high-performance connecting units which typically consist of a p-n junction. The P-type side of the junction is usually formed by metal oxides, while the n-type layer is mostly prepared by doping an electron-transporting layer(ETL) with a low work function metals[1-4]. In this work, we studied tandem OLEDs with a organic connecting layers which consisting of pentacene/C60 unit with the aim of understanding the factors influencing the device performance of tandem OLEDs.

2. RESULTS and DISCUSSION

The multilayer structure of tandem OLED was ITO/

NPB/Alq₃/C60/pentacene/NPB/Alq₃/LiF/ Al. Here, ITO, NPB, Alq₃, and pentacene/C60 were used as anode, hole-transporting layer, green light emitting layer/electron-transporting layer, and the connecting unit. When applying the reversed bias for the connecting unit, the charge generation phenomenon happened and injected into the adjoining electron-transporting layer and hole-transporting layer. So the recombination number of the electron-hole pair was increased and it raised the current efficiency in the device. In addition, lithium fluoride was used as a buffer layer and aluminum was the cathode.

Tandem devices exhibit a 34% improvement in current efficiency from 2.5 cd/A to 3.4 cd/A at a current density of 20 mA/cm², relative to the conventional device.. The maximum luminance was 6300 cd/m² at 27V.

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